

Study of the Impurities in Corroded Alloys

J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY

Department of Chemistry, P. S. G. College of Technology, Coimbatore-4

Manuscript received 5 November 1974; accepted 11 February 1975

The chemical analysis and supersonic measurements of some corroded Ag-Cu alloys have been studied. The heterogeneity increases not only owing to the amount of the impurities but also owing to the nature of the impurities, As the number of the main phases increases the heterogeneity in the total bulk also increases. The silver coated copper objects showed lesser heterogeneity than Ag-Cu alloys.

THE heterogeneity is due to an uneven or improper distribution of some insoluble impurities (like metallic oxides) in the medium and in an alloy it can be also due to improper mixing of the principal constituents. The heterogeneity may be defined as the change in the concentration of the components regularly or irregularly in the metallic piece and it may be of physical or chemical nature or both. Whenever the metal is subjected to such environments as produce corrosion, the chemical effect diffuses either on the surface or deep into the metallic object. The diffusion is usually continuous and the heterogeneity in such cases distributes itself in a continuous regular fashion. Even in such cases there is a centre of maximum heterogeneity round which it may vary in small degrees. There may be many such centres on the surface or in the metallic bulk.

The heterogeneity in a metallic object which may be present either in the crust or core is usually due to either corrosion^{1,2} or improper workmanship. Undoubtedly corrosion would increase with time, it may however, also vary with soil conditions and environments such as temperature and humidity. Apart from corrosion, factors causing heterogeneity may be considered as those caused by some phase of low solubility precipitated out at the time of manufacture, the imperfect fusion causing the metallic inclusions and the presence of slag or other nonmetallic material (such as oxides). However, the heterogeneity may also be due to segregation of components

on ageing by reason of diffusion, crystal growth or phase change, but this cause is not supported by photomicrograph studies³.

Besides the chemical analysis of corroded metallic objects⁴, a new technique which consists in passing the supersonic waves into corroded metallic objects to detect and estimate their heterogeneity has been developed⁵. This paper attempts to present a comparative study of chemical analysis and supersonic measurements of some corroded alloys to discuss the effect of the impurities on the heterogeneity.

Experimental

Before chemical analysis, the supersonic readings were noted for the samples. In pulse technique having a synchronizing generator, time base generator wide band amplifier, detector and output amplifier and liquid cell radiofrequency pulses are fed to the transducer (crystal) which acts as the source of the sound waves and generates accoustical pulses. These accoustical pulses upon completing a transit through the liquid cell are received by the receiver (crystal) which converts the accoustical pulses back to the electrical form. When a piece of metal or alloy is held perpendicular to the direction of the longitudinal waves, the waves are transmitted through this metallic object entirely as longitudinal waves. As the angle between the direction of longitudinal wave and the metallic object is decreased from 90°, a point comes when there is no transmission of longitudinal

TABLE I—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

No.	Ag (%)	Cu (%)	Zn (%)	Pb (%)	Fe (%)	As (%)	Sb (%)	Ni (%)	Sn (%)	S (%)	Total
1.	95.91	2.94	—	0.34	0.21	0.33	0.22	—	—	—	99.95
2.	96.73	1.53	0.56	0.39	0.36	0.35	—	—	—	—	99.92
3.	56.38	41.42	0.24	0.59	0.16	0.07	0.21	0.52	—	0.28	99.87
4.	56.25	41.43	—	0.74	0.39	0.19	—	0.54	—	0.34	99.88
5.	6.26	91.45	0.34	0.97	—	0.38	0.12	0.04	0.28	0.18	99.77
6.	3.88	94.86	0.42	0.96	—	0.49	0.16	0.01	0.53	0.18	99.71
7.	10.50	68.52	20.46	—	0.36	—	—	—	—	0.42	99.96
8.	12.45	76.02	11.00	0.13	0.23	—	—	—	—	0.14	99.97
9.	4.53	94.07	0.06	0.28	0.28	—	0.19	0.23	0.17	0.28	99.99

waves. This is the first critical angle (θ_1). As the metallic object continues to rotate a second critical angle is obtained at which shear waves in the metallic object also cease to be transmitted. This is the second critical angle (θ_2). Thus when this metallic object is rotated through 360° the total internal reflection takes place and four sets of critical angles (θ_1 and θ_2) result. If the metallic object is homogeneous the value of θ_1 will be the same in all four sets. Similar is the case with θ_2 . The closeness of the critical angles decreases as the heterogeneity in the metallic object increases and thus four different sets of critical angles can be observed. The extreme differences in the values of either θ or θ_2 in a set of four readings quantitatively exhibit the measure of heterogeneity for a given sample of the metallic object. Since,

$$\frac{V_L}{\sin \theta_1} = V'_L : \frac{V_L}{\sin \theta_2} = V'_s : \frac{V'_L}{V'} = K$$

(where V_L = Velocity of longitudinal waves in water, V'_s = Velocity of shear waves in the solid, and V'_L = Velocity of longitudinal waves in the solid). We get four different types of bulk constants viz., K_1, K_2, K_3 and K_4 in the case of a heterogeneous object. The maximum possible difference between them, ΔK , gives the amount of heterogeneity⁶. Naturally for a homogeneous object since $K_1 = K_2 = K_3 = K_4$.

ΔK will be equal to zero. Then the samples were analysed by using standard analytical procedures.

TABLE 2

No.	Variety (No) of impurities	Amount of impurities	O ₂ by difference	ΔK
1.	4	1.10	0.05	0.654
2.	4	1.66	0.08	0.689
3.	7	2.07	0.13	0.786
4.	5	2.20	0.12	0.753
5.	7	2.31	0.23	0.973
6.	7	2.82	0.29	1.012
7.	2	0.48	0.04	1.813
8.	3	0.50	0.03	1.952
9.	7	1.39	0.01	0.352

Discussion

The parameters of the heterogeneity are (1) corrosion, (2) improper purification of the metal from insoluble impurities like oxides, (3) improper mixing of the principal constituents in the case of an alloy⁷. The metallic samples studied here might have contained the soluble impurities originally. But on exposure to the environments these soluble impurities (metals) might have undergone changes (due to oxidation etc.); and become insoluble. Even these changes are not to the same extent and uniform which increase the heterogeneity.

The results show that the corrosion (O₂ %) and heterogeneity (ΔK values) are less as the Ag% increases in the alloys 1-6.

Here, the O₂ concentration percentage (found by the difference in analysis) cannot be taken as indicative of the extent of corrosion rate because the copper and copper base alloys are known to contain significant amounts of O₂ introduced into the metal during their manufacture. Thus it is difficult to isolate these two parameters of heterogeneity viz., (1) O₂ concentration due to corrosion. (2) O₂ concentration due to oxidation during manufacture. In addition, the presence of sulphur in appreciable amounts in these alloys constitutes another parameter of chemical corrosion. However, since all these factors are parameters of heterogeneity, their isolation may not be necessary in discussing the effect of impurities on heterogeneity. In these alloys the amount of impurities increases corrosion and heterogeneity. In alloy (4), however, the heterogeneity and corrosion decrease and this may be due to the lesser variety of impurities (impurities are five), compared to the alloy (3) (impurities are seven). Thus corrosion and heterogeneity increase not only owing to the amount of the impurities but also owing to the variety of the impurities. Alloys (7) and (8) show less amounts of impurities and corrosion but their heterogeneity (ΔK values) is high. This is due to the 3rd parameter of heterogeneity which becomes significant as these alloys contain three principle constituents (Cu-Ag-Zn). The alloy (9) shows very small amount of silver and the amount of impurities to considerable extent. But surprisingly, it shows very small amount of corrosion (O₂ %) and heterogeneity (ΔK). By the analysis of the blank (prepared by filing off a thin layer of surface metal from both sides and the edge of the object) which does not show the presence of silver, it is concluded that this alloy contains silver only as a coat. The bulk was protected from external corrosion and hence the heterogeneity did not increase.

Acknowledgement

The author is extremely grateful to Prof. G. R. Damodaran, Director and Dean of P.G. Studies, and Dr. R. Subbayan, Principal of PSG College of Technology for their kind encouragement in this work.

References

1. E. R. CALEY, *Proc. Amer. Phil. Soc.*, 1941, 84, 639.
2. E. T. HALL, *Archaeometry*, 1961, 41, 62.
3. E. R. CALEY, "Analysis of Ancient Metals". 1964, p. 31, 44.
4. PHILIPS, *J.C.S.*, 1852, 4, 252.
5. J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY, Ph.D. Thesis, Allahabad University, 1968. p. 27.
6. J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY, *J. Tech.*, 1973, 21, 96.
7. J. V. G. KRISHNAMURTHY, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1974, 23, 47.